

OPTIMIZATION OF CIRCULAR TRAINING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDURANCE OF PLAYERS AGED 16-17 YEARS

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Annotation: Today, in modern football, the distinction with hyperdynamic movements performed at great speed is clearly visible in all major championships.

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In our country, it is important to bring up a healthy and harmonious generation, to preserve the genafond of the nation, to form a healthy lifestyle in the family, in society, as one of the dominant directions of state policy. Improving the quality of physical education classes in educational institutions, organizing extracurricular activities and improving their effectiveness, developing and increasing the popularity of sports, choosing talented freestyle wrestlers and effectively using technical training for children, developing special endurance with the help of circular exercises is one of the pressing issues. It is difficult to imagine our national culture, the moral education of young people, in which the component of human culture is distinguished, without a conscious approach.

Football is a truly athletic game. It helps to develop agility, agility, endurance, strength and jumpiness. The player does an excessive amount of work during the game. This helps to raise the level of functional capabilities of a person to educate his spiritual-volitional qualities. Football, with its essence and content, quick and attractive actions displayed by goalkeepers and players during the game, technical and tactical combinations that attract the attention of people of older and younger age, not only millions of ordinary enthusiasts have gained a place of attention, but are embedded in the hearts of all state and public figures, artists and scientists, even very busy entrepreneurs.

If 7-8 hours of daily training are taken into account, then today's player will not require proof that during the annual season he will master extremely high volumes and large-scale current and gross loadings. By itself, it is known that such downloads cause local and global symptoms of exhaustion in the players' organism (primarily in the leg muscles). According to experts, each player 90 minutes 9-12 km. covering the distance, the same distance consists of more than 70-80 all movements, while playing elements such as running, jumping, glittering, turning, bending, falling and rotations, which are performed at most average and maximum speeds. So, one of the current attitudes of the "big" player today is to look for measures to regularly restore working capacity based on real physical and functional reserves. "Working capacity" is a multifaceted and comprehensive integral concept, the essence of which is determined by the sum of indicators of physical, functional, technical-tactical and psychological training.

In order to learn the experience of developing working skills in highly qualified players, an autonomous question program was developed. The survey involved 55 players

participating in the Uzbekistan national championship as respondents. The results obtained draw attention to the fact that the main part of the respondents (56.7-70%) did not have a clear idea of the volume of annual downloads, it became clear that after training and official competitions they would hiss fatigue for a long time (71.7%). It is known that after training or competition loads mastered during the day, symptoms of exhaustion are concentrated in the players' organism. However, 50% of respondents reported that they do not engage in such exercises. While the 50% of respondents who are engaged emphasize the speed-strength and running exercises, which are performed at great intensity in the morning "zaryadka" Sessions. According to the experts noted above, the use of such exercises in the morning on the eve of "waking up the body" will not only eliminate the symptoms of exhaustion, but can also lead to serious negative consequences.

Another important aspect is the sport, taking into account the rules of the competition the study of the competition process in which, having statistically studied the technique that is being used a lot, draw up tactical plans against it. In this process, it is necessary to plan training based on the annual competition calendar, to prepare athletes from 6 training sessions, depending on the amount of downloads, or from each month to the period of annual competitions, to prepare students, and in the end, to compare the overall, special training, improve the good results shown, eliminate the shortcomings of the loads, assessing the weekly norm allows you to assess whether the training is correct or incorrectly structured. In addition, before the main competitions, the athlete has a state of numbness, exhaustion. In this case, the training process is not structured incorrectly, but the training training training plan is incorrectly designed.

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